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Deliverable D2.6: Final report on implementation of security policies and procedures

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1 Introduction

As part of Deliverable 2.4 – “Full implementation of security policies and procedures”, the Inter-Operability Platform (IOP) software underwent a penetration test conducted by the forensic laboratory (FLAB) of the National Research and Education Network (NREN) of the Czech Republic (CESNET). SWITCH, the NREN of Switzerland, provided the installation that CESNET tested against. In accordance with Chapter 3, “Ongoing and Future Work”, from Deliverable 2.4 – “Full implementation of security policies and procedures”, this additional document outlines the results of this work.

The IOP is the middleware which enables the ScienceMesh and is described at length in deliverables D3.1 – “Initial definition of the protocols and APIs” and D3.2 – “Initial Implementation of the Platform - Demonstration”. Amongst other things, the IOP implements an invitation workflow which results in the exchange of tokens that allows users to share data and applications over different EFSS installations at different sites, starting from a message sent using an out-of-band channel (e.g. e-mail or instant messaging).

Note: In this document, several technical acronyms which are common in other project deliverables are used. Those not directly explained in the present document can be found in the [Science Mesh Glossary](#)¹.

2 Penetration Test

As the results of a penetration test are typically kept confidential, we will not present them here in full, but will show an overview of the outcome from the report without going into the details of the vulnerabilities. The detailed report has been forwarded to the relevant people within the Project on a need-to-know basis.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5038662>

2.1 Overview

The IOP software was under heavy development in 2022, as well as the ownCloud and Nextcloud-based ScienceMesh, which interface it with the relevant vendor software. For that reason, we conducted the penetration test in September of that year, in order to make sure that we obtained a snapshot of the system, which was representative of its final functionality. The code of the IOP is now more mature, making the results of the test more useful than if it had been conducted earlier to meet this deliverable's initially foreseen delivery date of end of 2021.

The aim of the penetration test was to test whether unauthorised access to services/data/systems can be obtained, or if data can be illegally modified/destroyed; if system/service availability can be inhibited or if authentication data can be obtained. Furthermore, it was tested whether the infrastructure can be misused to attack third-party networks and services and if vulnerabilities exist that could cause harm to the instance that has been tested.

2.2 Scope

The penetration test was solely focused on the IOP software and the components it required. The hardware and operating system running it were out of scope. It was assumed that the servers were patched according to the vendors' latest recommendations, as this is a requirement for joining the Science Mesh.

The various tests were done in a non-destructive manner, focusing on software vulnerabilities, leaving default passwords, running redundant services, and detecting devices and services that can be exploited to reflect flood attacks on the network layer.

2.3 Procedure

The expected findings of the penetration test included concrete suggestions for improving the level of protection of the IOP, an assessment of the threat potential of the Science Mesh infrastructure from the perspective of an attacker who could successfully compromise a service in the Demilitarised Zone (DMZ) and escalate their privileges on the system to root privileges, identification and countermeasure specifications of potential vulnerabilities in the IOP service from the perspective of a compromised site, and detailed recommendations for improving security.

The CESNET FLAB staff conducted the penetration tests on the computing environment to verify if unauthorized access to services/data/systems, unlawful modification/destruction of data, impairment of availability of services/systems, obtaining of authentication credentials, use of the infrastructure to attack third-party networks and services, or combinations of vulnerabilities that could lead to the aforementioned points were possible.

The technical implementation was carried out remotely from the FLAB's servers. In this way, the activity of a real attacker inside the network was simulated. The distributed scanner SNER, the Nessus tool, Burp suite, and Metasploit were used to collect data. Selected vulnerabilities and services were tested manually or by specialised tools.

The penetration tests that were conducted revealed a total of 8 vulnerabilities in various severity categories. A summary of all the vulnerabilities that were identified, including recommended measures to address them, can be found in a separate but classified document that was handed only to relevant actors within the Project about it. At the time the tests were performed, certain features of the IOP software were still in development and therefore were either unimplemented or unavailable in the test environment.

The performed tests were Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) and Remote Procedure Call (RPC) endpoint mapping, endpoint testing with BurpSuite (HTTP), BloomRPC (RPC), Code review (common vulnerabilities and application logic, go sec scanner) and manual application testing with the command line interface.

Most user data and project configuration are sanitised either by the strong-typing nature of the GO programming language (RPC marshalling, JSON struct mapping) or through explicit code (prepared statements, text vs HTML templates).

2.4 Findings

The penetration test that was conducted identified vulnerabilities in various categories, and in some cases also revealed inappropriate procedures for the deployment and operation of information systems. All the shortcomings that were identified were accompanied by recommendations for resolution.

Figure 1. Numbers of found Vulnerabilities and their Severity Level

The eight vulnerabilities that were identified during the tests included insecure handling of credentials (such as the presence of public logs, credentials in source codes, and deployments with default credentials) and the lack of use of Cross-Site Request Forgery (CSRF) tokens on some HTTP interfaces. These findings have been reported to the appropriate parties in order to address them. The only vulnerability affecting the REVA/IOP code base was promptly fixed. The installation documentation was also updated in order to make new participants aware of any such possible problems during the installation.

3 Concluding Remarks

Overall, the results of the penetration test are positive. There were only two serious vulnerabilities identified, one of high severity and one of medium severity, and both were easily mitigatable. The IOP software itself has proven to be very secure and not vulnerable to attacks, which is an important factor in building trust within the community of partners who will need to install it in order to join the Science Mesh.

It is recommended that the penetration test is repeated at regular intervals, as long as the software is being actively developed in order to ensure its continued security.